

The Level of Customer Service Satisfaction of Online App in Jollibee Waltermart Dasmaringas Cavite

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Abstract: The ultimate aim of this study is to know the satisfaction customer gets when they use this online app to order their food in Jollibee Waltermart Dasmaringas, with this study we will know what are the points that we need to consider when using online app in ordering food online that will be beneficial for students taking BSHRM course and entrepreneurs in the food industry. This study starts by knowing what are the common positive and negative effects do customers attained using this online app in ordering food when it comes to their demographic profile. Secondly know what is the main causes of this effects on customer satisfaction and lastly finalized the data by creating a tabulation of all data collected from the customers. Online survey in the form of google forms was use for methodology to gather data from 100 out of the population in Dasmaringas cavite who voluntary take the survey. Results indicated that majority of the people who use this application are female and people in the range of 25 years old and above that are single and employed are satisfied in using this online app in ordering food in Jollibee Waltermart Dasmaringas. A detailed and critical analysis of the results is provided in the last chapter.

Keywords: Food Delivery, Dasmaringas, Online App.

I. INTRODUCTION

Using online application in ordering food online is very essential now a days to all people especially to those working in their office and cannot go to a store to buy their food. Group of people, large businesses tend to order online for special occasions birthdays, parties and more. E-commerce has been one of the steadfastly rising industries in the Philippines. In 2018, the Internet World Stats found that more than 65 million Filipinos were active users of online services, with a predicted increase of 12% every year. As such, every business should take advantage of the use of online delivery in the Philippines. Considering that more Filipinos turn to services that offer delivery in the Philippines.

Due to this changes in the economy a lot of industries use this changes by creating online app in various services in all major industries. The industry that has a big impact on this is the food industry because a lot of people now a days cannot go to the store to buy their food and they prepare to eat their food in the office or at the house. To resolved this gap restaurant as well as fast food chain and delivery companies develop an online app that customers can use to order their food online without the hassle of going to the store and waiting on a long line, most common online app customers use in the Philippines is Food panda and Grab food etc. While most restaurants already have a direct, in-house delivery system in place in the past couple of decades, that did not stop anyone from developing new services to make the process more convenient for us. In 2010, local delivery service City Delivery was launched, which allowed people to order via a hotline or online from hundreds of restaurants in the Metro. The service was later acquired by app-based food delivery service Foodpanda, which arrived on our shores in 2014. Transport service Grab branched out into food deliveries with GrabFood in 2018, while the youngest app-based delivery service of the bunch, LalaFood, was launched in 2019.

The main objective of this study is to know the level of customer service satisfaction of online app in Jollibee Waltermart Dasmariñas that will be beneficial to all students taking the course of BSHRM, customers, entrepreneurs and as well as people who wish to use this online app in their businesses.

II. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE. This data collection will be used in gathering the data on the personal attributes of the participants in the research locale. The following variables that includes respondents profile are: Name, Age, Sex and Employment Status.

LEVEL OF CUSTOMER SERVICE SATISFACTION OF ONLINE FOOD APP IN JOLLIBEE WALTERMART DASMARINAS. The data collected under these tests were statistically treated and evaluated. And also, to know the customer service satisfaction respondents experience using online app of various online food delivery company in ordering food at Jollibee Waltermart Dasmariñas.

To know the level of customer service satisfaction, participants are asked to rate the four-point Likert scale; wherein:

Scale	Verbal Description
4	Strongly Agree
3	Neither Agree Nor Disagree
2	Disagree
1	Strongly Disagree

Data Treatment and Analysis

The researchers will use quantitative research and descriptive statistics, this method helps to determine the general trend in the study. The researchers used statistical tools which are to come to a clear conclusion on this study; frequency and percentage, measures of central tendency, particularly the mean and chi-square are used to examine the data and frequency tables.

Frequency and percentage, simply mean and chi-square was utilized to determine the level of customer service satisfaction of online app in Jollibee Waltermart Dasmariñas.

Frequency and percentage is a display of data that shows the number of observations for a group of data points in percentages.

To find the frequency and percentage, divide the frequency by the total number of results and multiply by 100.

Formula:

$$P = \frac{F}{N} \times 100$$

The mean is commonly used as an average for every category. This method also has the advantage of being simple and quick to calculate.

To find the mean, add all of the numbers in a set, then divide the sum by the total count of numbers.

Formula:

$$\text{Mean} = \frac{\text{Sum of all values in the data set}}{\text{Total no. of values in the data set}}$$

The Chi-square test is commonly used for determining if two categorical variables are related. The Chi-Square test's null hypothesis is that the categorical variables in the population have no connection; they are independent.

To determine the significant relationship between the demographic profile of the respondents and their perception in using online app in ordering food in Jollibee Waltermart Dasmariñas, Chi-square formula was utilized:

Formula:

$$\chi^2 = \sum \frac{(O_i - E_i)^2}{E_i}$$

Where:

χ^2 = chi-squared

O_i = observed value

E_i = expected value

For the statistical analysis that they have gathered, the researchers tallied the number of times a certain variable appeared in a category and calculated its percentage.

Using the formula and frequency table that is further elaborated, data are quantified throughout the results and discussion for a clear understanding of how the study's quantitative information is presented.

The researchers will thoroughly quantify and analyse the information gathered. Researchers were confident that the study would be successful if the right data analysis procedures were followed.

DEMOGRAPHIC DATA ANALYSES

1) What is the demographic profile of the respondent in terms of:

1.1 Age

Age	Frequency	Percent
18 years old and below	8	8
19,20	10	10
21,22	20	20
23,24	16	16
25 years old and above	46	46
Total	100	100

1.2 Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percent
Male	40	40
Female	60	60
Total	100	100

1.3 Marital Status

Marital Status	Frequency	Percent
Married	10	10
Single	90	90
Total	100	100

1.4 Employment status

Employment Status	Frequency	Percent
Employed	57	57
Self-Employed	9	9
Student	13	13
Unemployed	21	21
Total	100	100

2) What are the positive effects customer attained using this online app in ordering food online?

Verbal Interpretation:

- 1.00-1.49 Strongly Disagree
- 1.50-2.49 Disagree
- 2.50-3.49 Agree
- 3.50-4.00 Strongly Agree

Positive effects customer attained using this online in ordering food online	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
2.1 [I get the food right at my door step faster and in a good condition when using this online app]	3.75	Strongly Agree
2.1 [I am able to manage my time using this online app]	3.69	Strongly Agree
2.1 [I experience a good quality service while using this online app]	3.43	Agree
2.2 [I get my food at a cheaper price compare to the store when I use this online app]	3.33	Agree
Positive	3.55	Strongly Agree

3) What are the negative effects customer attained using this online app in ordering food online?

Negative effects customer attained using this online in ordering food online	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
2.2 [I experience in app problems while using this online app]	3.49	Agree
2.2 [I experience delayed deliveries when using this online app]	3.07	Agree
2.2 [I experience bad service such as food not properly pack, missing items and broken utensils when using this online app]	2.91	Agree
2.2 I get my food at a higher price compare to the original price at the store]	2.92	Agree
Negative	3.098	Agree

3) Is there any significant relationship between the negative and positive effects customer attained using this online app and their demographic profile with regards to the satisfaction in using this online app in ordering food in Jollibee Waltermart Dasmaringas?

Age vs	Chi-square Value	p-value	Interpretation
Positive	4.704	0.789	Not Significant
Negative	4.318	0.827	Not Significant

Interpretation: There is no significant relationship between age and their perception regarding the positive and negative effects, since the chi-square values of 4.704 and 4.318 have p-values greater than 0.05 significance level. The null hypothesis of no significant relationship are not rejected. Thus, age does not affect the perception of the customers regarding the positive and negative effects.

Gender vs	Chi-square Value	p-value	Interpretation
Positive	1.094	0.579	Not Significant
Negative	0.051	0.975	Not Significant

Interpretation: There is no significant relationship between gender and their perception regarding the positive and negative effects, since the chi-square values of 1.094 and 0.051 have p-values greater than 0.05 significance level. The null hypothesis of no significant relationship are not rejected. Thus, gender does not affect the perception of the customers regarding the positive and negative effects.

CIVIL STATUS vs	Chi-square Value	p-value	Interpretation
Positive	1.437	0.488	Not Significant
Negative	2.673	0.263	Not Significant

Interpretation: There is no significant relationship between civil status and their perception regarding the positive and negative effects, since the chi-square values of 1.437 and 2.673 have p-values greater than 0.05 significance level. The null hypothesis of no significant relationship are not rejected. Thus, civil status does not affect the perception of the customers regarding the positive and negative effects.

EMPLOYMENT STATUS vs	Chi-square Value	p-value	Interpretation
Positive	14.911	0.021	SIGNIFICANT
Negative	13.510	0.036	SIGNIFICANT

Interpretation: There is a significant relationship between employment status and their perception regarding the positive and negative effects, since the chi-square values of 14.911 and 13.510 have p-values less than 0.05 significance level. The null hypothesis of no significant relationship are rejected. Thus, employment status affects the perception of the customers regarding the positive and negative effects. Employed employees received to have lower positive and negative effect than other group of respondents.

III. CONCLUSION

The salient findings of this study are presented in this portion of the chapter, following the statement of the research problems presented earlier.

The following variables were considered in describing the profile of the respondents: sex, age and length of service.

Participants Demographic

1.1 Table 1 shows that 46% of the participants are in the age range of 25 years old and above, 20% are in the range of 21-22, 16% are in the range of 23-24 and 10% are in the range 19-20.

1.2 Table 2 shows that 60% of the respondents are female while 40% are males.

1.3 Table 3 shows that 90 of the respondents are single while 10% are married.

1.4 Table 4 shows that 57% of the respondents are employed, 21 % are unemployed, 9% are self-employed and lastly 13% are students.

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2.1 Table 5 shows that the total weighted mean in getting the positive effects customer attained using this online app in ordering food is 3.55 with a verbal interpretation of strongly agree.

2.2 Table 6 shows that the total weighted mean in getting the negative effects customer attained using this online app in ordering food is 3.098 with a verbal interpretation of agree

Significant relationship between the negative and positive effects customer attained using this online app and their demographic profile

3.1 Table 7 shows that there is no significant relationship between age and their perception regarding the positive and negative effects, since the chi-square values of 4.704 and 4.318 have p-values greater than 0.05 significance level. The null hypothesis of no significant relationship are not rejected. Thus, age does not affect the perception of the customers regarding the positive and negative effects.

3.2 Table 8 shows there is no significant relationship between gender and their perception regarding the positive and negative effects, since the chi-square values of 1.094 and 0.051 have p-values greater than 0.05 significance level. The null hypothesis of no significant relationship are not rejected. Thus, gender does not affect the perception of the customers regarding the positive and negative effects.

3.3 Table 9 shows There is no significant relationship between civil status and their perception regarding the positive and negative effects, since the chi-square values of 1.437 and 2.673 have p-values greater than 0.05 significance level. The null hypothesis of no significant relationship are not rejected. Thus, civil status does not affect the perception of the customers regarding the positive and negative effects.

3.4 Table 10 there is a significant relationship between employment status and their perception regarding the positive and negative effects, since the chi-square values of 14.911 and 13.510 have p-values less than 0.05 significance level. The null hypothesis of no significant relationship are rejected. Thus, employment status affects the perception of the customers regarding the positive and negative effects. Employed employees received to have lower positive and negative effect than other group of respondents.

IV. CONCLUSION OF THE STUDY

1. In general, majority of the respondents are female and people in the range of 25 years old and above that are single and employed are satisfied in using this online app in ordering food in Jollibee Waltermart Dasmarinas.
2. When it comes to the positive effects customer attained using this online app in ordering food online to get the level of customer service satisfaction majority of the respondents strongly agree that they experience positive effects.
3. When it comes to the negative effects customer attained using this online app in ordering food online to get the level customer service satisfaction majority of the respondents agree that they experience negative effects.
4. Furthermore, based on the findings the researchers conclude that the demographic profiles of the respondents in terms of age, gender, marital status and employment status has no significant relationship with their overall perceptions on the negative and positive effects customer attained using this online app in ordering food online Hence, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship was not rejected.

V. RECOMMENDATION

Based on our data collected and findings, we suggest to do further research on getting the customer service satisfaction on married male people who uses this online app in ordering food with age ranges from 19-20, 21-22 & 23-24 who are unemployed, self-employed and students and why they experience negative effects when using this online app that will be beneficial for future researcher who chooses to continue the same study and all HRM schools. We also suggest to have a more professionally designed data collecting instruments (questionnaire), in order to get higher accuracy and finer results.

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